

**NEW SUBSPECIES OF *MONOCHAMUS*
GALLOPROVINCIALIS (OLIVIER, 1795) FROM
CAUCASUS (COLEOPTERA: CERAMBYCIDAE)**

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ABSTRACT: *Monochamus galloprovincialis transitivus* ssp. n. close to *M. g. tauricola* Pic, 1912 is described from Transcaucasia and North Caucasus.

KEY WORDS: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, *Monochamus*, taxonomy, new subspecies, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Georgia, Armenia

Monochamus galloprovincialis (Olivier, 1795) was described from Provence (South France) on the base of specimens with red head and antennae. The nominative subspecies is distributed in the West Europe occurring in Spain, Portugal, France and Italy (Sicily) as well as in North Africa. Central and East Europe is occupied by *M. g. pistor* (Germar, 1818) described from Europe ("Krain", "Curland" – Slovenia and Latvia) with black head and antennae. Siberian specimens are characterized by usually glabrous elytra without pubescence spots, though single pubescent specimens are known. Siberian subspecies could be accepted (Danilevsky, 2012) as *M. g. cinerascens* (Motschulsky, 1860) described from "Daourie". The most pubescent specimens are known from Near East (Syria, Jordan, South Turkey). Those populations were accepted (Danilevsky, 2012) as *M. g. tauricola* Pic, 1912 (fig. 5) described from "Taurus cilicien". Populations from Caucasus and Transcaucasia were joined by Danilevsky (2012) to *M. g. tauricola* Pic, 1912, though local populations demonstrate less pubescent elytra and are described bellow as a new subspecies.

Several abbreviations are used in the text:

MD – collection of M. Danilevsky (Moscow, Russia)

ZMM – Zoological Museum of Moscow State University (Moscow, Russia)

***Monochamus galloprovincialis transitivus* ssp. n.**

(Figs. 1-4)

Type locality. Georgia, Borzhomi environs.

The subspecies is characterized by strong development of body pubescence, though less than in *M. g. tauricola* Pic, 1912.

Dorsal head surface with distinct orange pubescence, anterior parts of antennal tubercles with white pubescence; pronotum with scattered orange pubescence strongly concentrated behind lateral thoracic spines; scutellum densely covered by orange pubescence with short narrow anterior glabrous stroke; elytra in males nearly parallelsided (strongly tapering posteriorly in *M. g. tauricola*), in females – slightly widened near middle; anterior diffuse transverse elytral band is more or less orange with several white setae spots; central transverse band (white in males, orange in females) relatively contrast (much more contrast in *M. g. tauricola*); posterior elytral parts in males with mixed

white and orange spots; body length in males: 15.6-22.0 mm, width: 4.8-6.9 mm, length in females: 17.0-23.5 mm, width: 5.5-7.8 mm.

Materials. Holotype, male, "Borjom-Geb. / Cauc. 4.VIII" – ZMM; 8 paratypes; 1 male, 1 female, Caucasus, Ubinskoe, 18.VI.1970, M.Danilevsky leg. – MD; 1 female, same locality 15.VII.1970 – MD; 1 female, Georgia, Ritsa Lake, 19.8.1976 – MD; 1 female, N Caucasus, Teberda, 17.8.1982, O.Gorbunov – MD; 1 male, Armenia, Khosrov, 4.7.1983, M.Danilevsky leg. – MD; 1 female, "Transcauc. / Gruzia / AbasTuman / VII" – ZMM; 1 female, "Transcaucasia / Agghi-Dagh / Mons Tschuchur- / Tscham 8500-9000 p. / 24.VII.1911 E.Miller" – ZMM.

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Figure 1-2. *Monochamus galloprovincialis transitivus* ssp. n.: 1. Holotype, male, "Borjom-Geb. / Cauc. 4.VIII"; 2. Holotype labels.

Figure 3-5. *Monochamus galloprovincialis transitivus* ssp. n.: 3. Paratype, male, Caucasus, Ubinskoe, 18.VI.1970, M.Danilevsky leg.; 4. Paratype, female with same labels; 5. *Monochamus galloprovincialis tauricola* Pic, 1912: "TURKEY / 15.5-26.05.2010 / Kemer distr., Beldibi env. / Taurus mnt. / leg. Safronov D.A." – MD.